

**DIFFERENCES AND INTERRELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN
SOCIOLINGUISTIC AND PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE**

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***Аннотация.** Статья посвящена анализу социолингвистической и прагматической компетенций как компонентов коммуникативной компетенции. Социолингвистическая компетенция рассматривается как способность использовать язык в соответствии с социокультурным контекстом, включая знание регистров речи и норм вежливости. Прагматическая компетенция определяется как умение эффективно применять языковые средства для достижения коммуникативных целей. Выявлены ключевые различия: социолингвистическая компетенция фокусируется на социокультурной уместности, прагматическая — на функциональной эффективности коммуникации. Показано, что обе компетенции тесно взаимосвязаны и функционируют совместно в реальном общении. Подчеркивается важность их интегрированного развития в языковом образовании для успешной межкультурной коммуникации.*

***Ключевые слова:** социолингвистическая компетенция, прагматическая компетенция, коммуникативная компетенция, межкультурная коммуникация, языковое образование, лингвистическая прагматика, социокультурный контекст*

***Abstract.** The article is dedicated to the analysis of sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies as components of communicative competence. Sociolinguistic competence is considered as the ability to use language in accordance with the sociocultural context, including knowledge of speech registers and politeness norms. Pragmatic competence is defined as the ability to effectively use language tools to achieve communicative goals. Key differences were identified: sociolinguistic competence focuses on sociocultural appropriateness, pragmatic competence on the functional effectiveness of communication. Both competencies are closely interconnected and function together in real communication. The importance of their integrated development in language education for successful intercultural communication is emphasized.*

***Key words:** sociolinguistic competence, pragmatic competence, communicative competence, intercultural communication, language education, linguistic pragmatics, sociocultural context*

The formation of communicative competence is a central task of modern language education. In the structure of communicative competence, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies hold a special place, which, despite the significant intersection of functional areas, represent independent components of language proficiency. Understanding the differences and interrelationships between these competencies is crucial for both linguo-didactics theory and foreign language teaching practice.

The problem of distinguishing sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies has attracted the attention of many researchers (Bachman, 1990; Canale & Swain, 1980; Council of Europe, 2001; Hymes, 1972). However, to date, there is no unified

approach in the scientific literature to defining the boundaries and points of contact of these competencies.

Sociolinguistic competence is understood as an individual's ability to use language in accordance with the social context of communication. As Canale (1983) notes, sociolinguistic competence includes knowledge of the sociocultural rules of language use and discourse. This competency encompasses mastering registers, speech styles, dialects, and sociolects, as well as understanding the social meanings of language forms.

According to the Concept of Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages, 2001), sociolinguistic competence reflects the sociocultural conditions of language use and includes: markers of social relations, rules of politeness, expressions of folk wisdom, register differences, dialects, and accents.

Van Ek (1986) emphasizes that sociolinguistic competence requires awareness of the social meanings of linguistic forms and the ability to choose and use appropriate forms depending on the communication situation, communication participants, and communicative goals.

An important aspect of sociolinguistic competence is the mastery of socially determined language variants. Studies by Labov (1972) and Trudgill (1974) show that speakers vary in their speech depending on social class, age, gender, ethnicity, and other social parameters. The ability to recognize and appropriately use such variants constitutes the essence of sociolinguistic competence.

Pragmatic competence is defined as the ability to use language to achieve communicative goals and understand the language in its context of use. According to Thomas (1993), pragmatic competence includes the ability to use language effectively to achieve a specific goal and the ability to recognize the language used indirectly or implicitly.

Leech (1993) distinguishes between the pragmalinguistic and sociopragmatic components of pragmatic competence. Pragmalinguistics deals with linguistic resources for expressing illokutive power and implementing speech acts, while sociopragmatics is concerned with the social conditions for the appropriateness of language use.

According to Bachman (1990), pragmatic competence consists of illocutionary competence (the ability to perform and interpret speech acts) and sociolinguistic competence (the ability to use language in accordance with the context). This interpretation shows a close relationship between these competencies.

Kasper (1997) views pragmatic competence as knowledge of communicative action and its implementation methods, as well as the ability to use language for various functions. The central components of pragmatic competence are knowledge of speech acts, discourse conventions, implicatures, and presuppositions.

Despite the significant intersection of functional areas, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies have significant differences. The main difference lies in the focus of attention: sociolinguistic competence focuses on the social variation of language and the sociocultural adequacy of linguistic behavior, while pragmatic competence emphasizes the functional use of language to achieve communicative goals. As noted by Bialystok (1997), sociolinguistic competence is related to the choice of linguistic forms corresponding to the social status of communication participants, their relationships, and communication situations. Pragmatic competence, on the contrary, relates to the use of language to perform communicative functions such as asking, apologizing, refusing, regardless of social context.

Rose and Kasper (2001) distinguish between sociopragmatic and pragmalinguistic knowledge. Sociopragmatic knowledge represents an understanding of the social conditions and consequences of pragmatic choices, which brings it closer to sociolinguistic competence. Pragmalinguistic knowledge includes conventions of means for the implementation of communicative acts, which is a pragmatic field. Within the framework of sociolinguistic competence, emphasis is placed on the social stratification of language, registers, styles, forms of address, expressions of politeness, which mark social relations. Pragmatic competence is largely connected with speech acts, implications, deixis, presuppositions, and the organization of discourse. Despite the differences, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies are closely interconnected and largely interdependent. Celce-Murcia, Dörnyei, and Thurrell (1995) propose a model of communicative competence in which sociocultural and relevant (including pragmatic aspects) competencies are presented as interacting components.

The interrelationship is especially evident in the area of politeness. Brown and Levinson's (1987) theory of politeness shows that the realization of speech acts (pragmatic aspect) is inextricably linked to considering social variables such as social distance, power, and the degree of imposition (sociolinguistic aspect). Choosing a politeness strategy is both a pragmatic and sociolinguistic decision. Bardovi-Harlig (1999) argues that the development of pragmatic competence is impossible without considering sociolinguistic factors. Foreign language learners should not only know what speech acts are possible in a given situation, but also how they are implemented differently depending on the social context. Studies of intercultural pragmatics

(Wierzbicka, 2003; Spencer-Oatey 2007) demonstrate that pragmatic norms are deeply rooted in socio-cultural values and practices. Understanding and adequately using indirect speech acts, implications, and irony requires not only pragmatic knowledge but also sociolinguistic awareness of cultural conventions and social norms.

Moreover, both competencies are related to the concept of context. Sociolinguistic competence requires consideration of the social context, while pragmatic competence requires consideration of the situational and discursive context. However, these types of context are not independent: the social context influences the interpretation of pragmatic meaning, and pragmatic choices reflect and construct social relations. According to Savignon (2007), for the development of sociolinguistic competence, it is necessary to familiarize students with various registers, styles, social dialects, as well as culturally determined norms of linguistic behavior. Developing pragmatic competence requires learning to recognize and produce speech acts, understand implications, and organize discourse.

An integrated approach to developing both competencies involves the use of authentic materials reflecting real language use in various social contexts, role-playing and simulation that allow for practicing sociolinguistically and pragmatically adequate language behavior, as well as metapragmatic reflection (Ishihara & Cohen, 2010).

Sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies represent different, yet interconnected components of communicative competence. Sociolinguistic competence focuses on the social variation of language and the correspondence of linguistic behavior to sociocultural norms, while pragmatic competence focuses on the functional use of language to achieve communicative goals. However, these competencies are closely intertwined, especially in the areas of politeness, speech acts, and consideration of context. Effective formation of communicative competence requires an integrated approach to the development of both sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies, which should be reflected in the programs and methodologies for teaching foreign languages.

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